

Ethno-Religious Conflicts: A Challenge To National Integration In Nigerian Contemporary Society

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Abstract

Nigeria is a democratic country with diverse cultures, different ethnic groups, and religions. The crisis of integration in Nigerian contemporary society is very severe. This situation provoke concern and interest in public discourse and intellectual circle. Most of these crisis are constructed from differences in religious and ethnic identities, whereby the groups involved were inoculated with dangerous ideas of intolerance. This amounts to ethno-religious clashes, unequal allocation of resources, economic decline, unbalanced political structure and political struggle to be in control of power. All these culminate to a strong pressure on Nigeria nation with the tendency to disintegrate. With this infinitesimal background, this paper therefore aims at examining and evaluating the complexity and diversity of ethnicity and religious conflicts in contemporary Nigeria society. It used the secondary qualitative method for its data collection, while the analysis is basically descriptive. This paper identifies the causes of ethno-religious crisis that impede the possible co-existence among groups, despite democratization of Nigerian nation. This paper proffers some recommendations that will ameliorate the problems of ethno-religious conflicts and promote peace, justice, equity, fairness, national unity and integration.

Key words: identity, cultural identity, ethnicity, religious identity, national integration

Introduction

Nigeria is a democratic country as well as a heterogeneous nation with diverse cultures, multi-ethnic groups and different religions; because of these differences in cultural values, ethnicity and religious beliefs, clashes and conflicts are unavoidable. These clashes and conflicts are as a result of competitions, confrontations and threat by other people from different cultural background. In this

contemporary time, Nigeria as a country is witnessing series of violence ranging from ethnic violence to religious violence and finally to political violence. These conflicts pose big threat to the unity of the country and have devastating effect on peaceful co-existence, and probably making people to live in fear in their homeland.

Nigeria of today is a pluralistic society, with different cultural and religious groups.

Pluralism according to Ekwunife (1992, p.17) involves

Awareness on the part of those affected, of the existential differences in cultural behaviour, philosophy of life and even certain attitudes and values. It further implies a conscious acceptance of these differences as inevitable in search for significant and relevant common goals, objectives and philosophy which take cognizance of common needs, aspirations and values of different ethnic groups within the same nation.

Nigeria's component groups are separated from each other by revelatory differences of languages and ethnicity. Different cultural backgrounds of Nigeria citizens created differences in attitude, character and general outlook. These differences meet and clash, and resulted to different crisis and conflicts we have been witnessing in Nigeria from the earlier history till present.

Nigeria as a country came into corporate existence as a result of the 1914 amalgamation. That is the unification of the Northern and Southern protectorates by the British colonizer which was effected by Sir Frederick Lugard. Amalgamation should be on the grounds of agreement of unification, in the sense that parties involved should be integrated with one another for the purposes of coexistence, co-administering and co-sharing of the country's resources, and co-development of the country. Instead, the amalgamation brought about

aggressive inter-ethnic competition and tension, which gave rise to struggling for ethnic survival. This led to the problem of who will be in charge. As a result, crisis and violence have been on the increase. These crisis and violence are getting to the climax, and if they are not controlled, could lead to the disintegration of the country.

Nigeria's move for survival started since the amalgamation of the country in 1914. Owing to the above claim to three dimensional suspicion and distrust amongst the various ethnic groups and their religions, ethnicity became a key issue in defining social relation in our various communities (Umar, 2014). More so Umar Ardo added that the issue of ethnicity later became so pronounced that it turned to be the most serious element militating against Nigeria's national integration and unity, leaving a doubt whether the country would be capable of attaining national integration (Umar, 2014). Umar Ardo further identified major barriers for sustainable national unity and integration *vis-à-vis* "ethnic and religious sentiments" (Umar, 2014).

The problems generated by different values in our various cultures encourage ethnicity and religious sentiment, which brought about tussle to be in control of power and allocation of the country's resources. The above problem fuelled the corruption pandemic and increased the degree of looting of the country's resources. These provoked all forms

of public unrest and the quest for disintegration. This paper therefore, examines the relationship between ethnicity and religion in connection to crises and national disintegration. It identifies the causes of ethno-religious crisis. Some recommendations are made to ameliorate the problems of ethno-religious conflict and promote peace, justice, equity, fairness, national unity and integration.

Theoretical Framework

This work utilizes Immanuel Kant's theory of categorical imperative. In this theory, Kant argues that individuals should be duty bound to do what is right notwithstanding the condition or intention of those performing the act. This is because hypothetical moral system cannot persuade moral action or be regarded as bases for moral judgment against others since the imperatives on which they are based rely much on subjective consideration. Kant viewed the human individual as a rationally self-conscious being with impure freedom of choice. Pure practical reason is the process of determining what ought to be done without reference to empirical contingent factors. In his own words, Kant stated that, "act only according to that maxim whereby you can at the same time will that it should become a universal law" (Kant, 1993). Therefore, all people should consider themselves never solely as means but always as ends. It is not perfect to act by maxim that creates incoherent or impossible states of natural affairs. Kant's categorical imperative

explains the ethical or moral obligation binding in all conditions and it is independent of any personal interests and inclination.

This theory is therefore, recommended as a foundation upon which the democratic structure in Nigeria could be constructed. This is because it is understood as an ideal moral principle rooted in selflessness. Introducing false ethical values or wrong religious values will destroy the peace and unity of the country since it is obvious that the root causes of ethno-religious conflicts include corruption, ethnicity, religious intolerance, lack of fairness, equity and social justice. There is need to apply the theory. This will help to ameliorate or even stop a good number of conflicts associated with ethnicity and religion. The practical adoption of the theory will encourage a higher sense of integration, thereby resulting in the common good and a just society. If the theory is properly inculcated, this will change the moral will and encourage a strong formation of worthy mindsets of the leaders and the led. By doing this, there will be peaceful co-existence, unity and integration in the country.

Conceptual Clarification

Identity

Identity can be viewed from different perspectives. It is mainly relational and has little to do with personal attributes like habits, ideals, constitutions, etc. Identity is defined by Mish (2004, p.616) as, "the distinguishing

character or personality of an individual; the condition of being the same with something described or asserted; an equation that is satisfied for all values of the symbols.” It is all about what people have in common and what differentiates them. To elaborate more, a person’s identity is the totality of one’s self-construal, in which how one construes oneself in the present expresses the continuity between how one construes oneself as one was in the past and how one construes oneself as one aspires to be in future (Weinreich, 1986).

Identity is all about how one perceives one’s self, that is, the definition of one-self. According to Weeks (1990: p.88) identity basically gives you a sense of personal location and the stable core to your individuality. It is all about belonging, since knowing who you are and knowing where you come from can give you a sense of belonging. Who we are as individual links us to the people we share a common identity. Identities are constructed by an integral connection of language, social structures, gender orientation and cultural patterns (Communication Theory, 2018). Our connection to others is the main key to survival, happiness, our being successful and failures.

Cultural Identity

To arrive at the definition of cultural identity, there is need to consider the concept of culture, which is the people’s way of life. According to Federal Republic of Nigeria

(1988, p.5), Culture Policy for Nigeria defined culture as,

The totality of the way of life evolved by a person in their attempts to meet the challenge of living in their environment, which gives order and meaning to their social, political, economic, aesthetic and religious norms and modes of organization: thus distinguishing a people from their neighbours.

Culture originates from man’s response to diversities and dynamics of his environment, which constitute the whole ways of life (Enebe, 2018). Therefore, culture is very instrumental in giving identity to people and groups, to ensure survival and enhance the feeling of belonging. No man is an island; person’s survival depends on another human person’s effort. Human beings are social animals in the sense that they desire to live in the company of others. Man develops and learns about his environment through the filter of others. There is this tendency that man desire to belong and be part of a group, and there is a shared sense of interest, beliefs and companionship, among others. When one identifies with a certain culture, it means that they are ready to carry on the heritage of that particular culture, thereby identifying with both internal and external elements associated with the culture in question. Culture here is seen as an important factor in shaping identity (Pratt, 2005).

Cultural identity is defined as the identity or feeling of belonging to a group. It is part of

a person's self-conception and self-perception and is related to nationality, ethnicity, religion, social class, generation, locality or any kind of social group that has its own distinct culture. In this way cultural identity is both characteristics of the individual and a culturally identical group of members sharing the same cultural identity (Moha, 2005). Cultural identity can also be viewed as, familial and cultural dimensions of a person's identity, and how others perceive that particular person, that is, factors that are salient to a person's identity both as perceived by the individual and how others perceive the person's identity (Ibrahim and Heuer, 2016).

More so, cultural identity is self-identification, a sense of belonging to a group that reaffirms itself. It is the extent to which one is a representative of a given culture behaviourally, communicatively, psychologically and sociologically. It also consists of values, meanings, customs and beliefs used to relate to the world. It reflects the common historical experiences as its shared cultural codes, which makes us one entity in a stable, unchanging, continuing frame of reference and meaningful society (Communication Theory, 2018). Feeling 'belonged' is one of the main reason people want to gain cultural identity. This is because from the element of belonging, people can draw their inner power to rise above their situation in the society. Cultural identity is dynamic and

constantly evolving, as it covers the entire life span of human beings and changes every moment based on social context (Communication Theory, 2018). Without the sense of cultural identity, it is easy for one to be overwhelmed by pressure in the society.

Ethnicity

Ethnicity is the fact or state of belonging to a social group that has a common national or cultural tradition (British and World English, 2018). Nnoli (1973, p.58) defined ethnicity as, "the social phenomenon associated with interaction among members of different ethnic groups refer to social formation distinguished by the communal character of the boundaries of which their common factors may be language, culture or both." Nigeria is a democratic country with diverse cultures, different ethnic groups, languages, religions and traditions (Onuorah, 2016). Since Nigeria as a country has over 250 ethnic groups (Central Intelligence Agency, 2016), ethnicity is bound to exist in such a political society. According to the data from Central Intelligence Agency, the most populous and influential ethnic groups in Nigeria are the Hausa and Fulani 29%, Yoruba 21%, Igbo 18%, Ijaw 10%, Kanuri 4%, Ibibio 3.5% and Tiv 2.5% (Central Intelligence Agency, 2016). Eriksen (1996, p.30) observed that ethnicity is characterized by, "a common consciousness of being one in relation to the other group."

In ethnicity, tribal affiliation is very strong and visible. Some individuals choose to abuse ethnicity for their tribal interest, which encourages corruption and nepotism. Almost all the activities in Nigeria government have ethnic discrimination, be it politics, employment, admission to tertiary institutions and provision of social amenities, among others. A good number of principles of ethnicity are used by political leaders and other important personalities to frame their arguments on how things could be run in the society. The first one is the use of ethnic identity, which is the most important and consistent basis of social identity in the country. Secondly, ethnicity is seen as a way for collective action; and finally, ethnicity is presumed to be a destabilizing factor with far reaching impacts on democracy (Lewis, 2007). The above have devastating results like marginalization, promotion of individualistic and ethnic interest (as in ethnic resource control), practice of sectional and tribal politics, and propagation of exclusive religious ideologies, among others. Conflict is therefore inevitable in ethnicity because of the abuse, and it hinders the nation's progress and development. Lewis (2007, p.2) further observes that, "because political competition is played along the line of ethnicity, the resultant 'democracy' but authoritarian government ostensibly has an ethnic character."

Religious Identity

Religion is the medium through which man attempts to comprehend his nature, the nature of things around him both animate and inanimate, the universe and the supernatural being (Onuorah, 2018 p.205), in connection with the rituals and ceremonies attached to them. To belong to a religion means to share with the belief system by participating in the ritual and ceremonies of that religion. Religious identity describes how a person or group understands, experiences, shapes, and is shaped by the psychological, social, political, and devotional facets of religious belonging or affiliation (Jackson II and Hogg, 2018).

There are diversities within each religion in terms of how the adherents define their connection to their lives. For some, religion's theological beliefs and rituals of worship are central to their lives. Others are more drawn to a religion's community and culture than to its beliefs and rituals. Many even feel part of a religion's culture but choose not to participate in its rituals at all. Some people feel free to choose a religion for themselves, or to reject religion entirely as a part of their identity. Others feel that they have been born and raised in a particular religion and are unwilling or unable to change it. Some governments grant privileges to one religion and not to others, while other governments protect citizens' freedom to follow any religion without

privilege or penalty (Facing History and Ourselves, 2017).

Nigeria as a country has three major religious identities *vis-à-vis* Christianity, Islam and traditional religion (Omogbe and Omohan, 2005). Among these three major religions, the first two groups (Christianity and Islam) dominate the last group (traditional religion). Based on World Population Prospects (2015, p. 21), “Nigeria is the most crowded African country with a population of about 182 million.” This population of people is divided about equally between Christianity and Islam. Pew Research Centre Forum in 2009 declared 46% for Christians, 52% for Muslims and 1 % for others (Pew Research Centre, 2010). Nigeria has been witnessing series of periodic violence for decades as a result of religious intolerance from the adherents of these major religious groups. Christian and Muslim identities are known for being in religious disparity and conflict. Therefore, the main forms of religious conflicts in Nigeria are between the Muslims and the Christians. The traditional religion on the other hand is hardly seen having problems that would result to crises or conflict with any of the two other groups.

National Integration

National integration is made up of two word, nation and integration. In order to understand the meaning, there is the need to get clear definitions of the words that made up the

phenomenon. The word ‘national’ is got from the root word ‘nation’. Nation according to Oxford Dictionaries (2018) is, “a large body of people united by common descent, history, culture or language, inhabiting a particular state or territory.” It is a large body of people, associated with a particular territory that is sufficiently conscious of its unity to seek or to possess a government peculiarly its own (Dictionary.com).

The word ‘integration’ is defined as, the act of combining or adding parts to make a unified whole; the act of amalgamating a racial or religious groups with an existing community; the combination of previously racially segregated social faculties into nonsegregated system (Collins English Dictionary, 2018). Integration occurs when separate people or thing are brought together. It is the combination of two or more things into an integral whole.

From the above definitions, national integration is the practical coming together of the people of different histories, cultures, religions, languages and ethnicity to one unified territorial society. National integration can also be seen as the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country (Khurana, 2018). To elaborate more, national integration is the feeling of togetherness or oneness towards one’s own country irrespective of their individual differences with regards to religion, region, race, culture, or caste. It also involves a feeling that brings

people from all areas, dialects and beliefs together in a common endeavor (Singh, 2017).

Nigeria as a country belongs to different ethnicity, religions and cultures, and speaks different languages. The true fact that Nigeria is a country brought these differences under one nation. National integration therefore, combines these differences and makes individuals to work together as a unified force to build up strong systems that enhance national unity, prosperous nation and a peaceful co-existence between the citizens with different socio-cultural backgrounds

Ethno-Religious Conflicts

Ethno-religious conflict is a conflict that involves different ethnic groups that belong to different religions. Before colonialism there was nothing like religious crisis. The whole ethnic group was dominated by the adherents of the traditional religion. There were ethnic or tribal clashes and wars at this period, but the increasing acts of violence between ethnic groups and religious groups in this contemporary time are so alarming. Those involved in ethnic conflicts are with long histories of tension and suffering from post-colonial deprivation, political and economic instability.

The colonial period in Nigeria recorded waves of changes, which were introduced by the colonial masters who were solely concerned about their administrative conveniences and

personal gains. Colonialism brought about the introduction of Christianity and Islam. Therefore, the seed of religious intolerance that causes religious conflict in Nigeria was sown through the agencies of colonialism, Islam and Christianity (Ekwunife, 1992). Ibrahim Musa Ahmadu (1990, cited in Ekwunife 1992, p.18), observed that

The presence of oriental religions in Nigeria thrust a discordant note into this serene religious atmosphere. Throughout the history of their developments Islam and Christianity have co-existed in mutual hostility. Though emerging from the same roots with almost identical literature and tenets, their strides for proselytization have often been marked by violence and intolerance.

Boko Haram

Boko Haram is a militant and violent Islamic organization established in North East Nigeria in 2002. They are also active in Niger, Chad, and Cameroon. The word origin of Boko Haram is from Hausa and Arabic language; translated as ‘western education is forbidden’ (Collins English Dictionary, 2018). Boko Haram, whose Arabic name is Jama’atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda’awati wal-jihad, meaning “People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet’s Teachings and Jihad” was founded in 2002 by Mohammed Yusuf in order to oppose Western education. Its objective has expanded to create an Islamic state in Nigeria (Genocide Watch, 2015). At its inception, Boko Haram was not

violent. It changed in 2009, when some of its members were arrested, which started a riot as well as armed clash with the Nigerian Army that killed about 800 people. In the wake of 2009 riots, Boko Haram turned to horribly violent group (Genocide Watch, 2015).

Since 1999 till date, Nigeria has continued to experience series of ethno-religious conflicts. The Nigeria Social Violence Dataset, tallies the incidents of deadly social violence in Nigeria since 1998, the eve of the most recent transition to democracy. Drawn from Nigerian and international media reports, the dataset provides dates, location, protagonists and lines of division in thousands of incidence. The data makes it clear that Boko Haram-related violence is the most lethal conflict that Nigeria has confronted in decades. Since 1998, at least 29,600 Nigerians have been killed in more than 2,300 incidents reflecting a wide range of ethnic, religious, political and economic tensions across large portions of the country. Since July 2009, when the Boko Haram conflict escalated, at least 11,100 people have died on all sides of the insurgency. This accounts for almost 40% of the total deaths in our dataset, more than any other source (Washington Post, 2014). Boko Haram killings in Nigeria made the Global Terrorist Index to rank Nigeria third in 2015 and 2016 most terrorized country (Ukpong, 2017).

Governor Shettima of Borno State released a grim statistics of deaths and

materials losses suffered by the State due to the Boko Haram insurgency, in his paper titled “Managing Boko Haram Crisis in Borno State, Experiences and Lessons for a Multiparty, Multiethnic and Multireligious Nigeria.” According to Tukur (2017), Shettima revealed in Premium Times that Boko Haram insurgency has led to the death of almost 100,000 persons going by the estimate of the community leaders over the years; 2,114,000 persons have become internally displaced as at December, 2016 with 537,815 in separate camps; 158,201 are at official camps that consists of six centres with two transit camps at Muna and Customs house, both in Maiduguri.

There are 379,614 internally displaced persons (IDPs) at 15 satellite camps comprising Ngala, Monguno, Bama, Banki, Pulka, Gwoza, Sabon Gari and other locations in the State. 73,404 persons were forced to become refugees in neighbouring countries with Niger and Cameroon having 62,002. Official records show 52,311 orphans who were separated and unaccompanied, 54,911 widows who lost their husband to insurgency and about 9,012 returned back to their various communities. The inflicted damages tune to the sum of \$9 billion on the region, of this amount, the destruction in Borno State amounts to \$6 billion and they are supported by statistics (Tukur, 2017).

Herdsman (Fulani)

The herdsman that are familiar with Nigeria environment and are known in Nigerian society is Fulani herdsman. The Fulani in Nigeria are a part of the Peul, or Fula ethnic group, which has existed in some form for thousands of years (Burton, 2017). The largest community of Fulani in Africa is located in Nigeria, where they make up one of the nation's largest ethnic group. The Fula people are almost solely Muslims. Most Fulani maintained a semi-nomadic lifestyle, earning them the appellation of "Fulani herdsman". The current struggle between the Fulani and other people of Nigeria represents the end result of years of conflict between the Fulani and others in the area and results from many social, economic and environmental factors that have long affected the Fulani (Burton, 2017).

Today, Nigeria's Fulani constitute the fourth-largest ethnic group nationally, with the population of over 7 million. Because of the nomadic lifestyle of the Fulani in Nigeria, they have long competed with other communities like Hausa for land and these conflicts have only increased since the 1999 democratization of Nigeria (Burton, 2017). In the past, the Fulani have engaged in fighting with other local groups, especially the Jukun, Eggon, and Tiv communities. Their disputes with these communities primarily focused around land disputes, though religious concerns have fueled the violence as well. The history of the Fulani

and their nature as pastoralists has contributed significantly to the burgeoning conflict at hand (Burton, 2017). The ethnic conflict between the Fulani and the farming communities over land grazing brought hostility and threat to the fragile region. The Fulani are accused of rape, kidnapping and murder. They also resort to terrorist activities. The Global Terrorism Index compiles a list of the world's most terrorist organization and ranked Fulani militant as number four in the list (Buchanan, 2015).

From 1996 to 2006, about 121 people lost their lives in Bauchi and Gombe States as a result of conflicts between Fulani herdsman and farmers. Between 2010 and 2013, 80 people were killed by Fulani militants. In 2013, Nigeria's Fulani ethnic militia caused 63 deaths. In 2014, they were responsible for 1,229 deaths. In the first quarter of 2016, Fulani ethnic militia was responsible for nearly 500 deaths. In January 2016, about 500 Agatu villagers in Benue State lost their lives to herdsman. In April 2016, Fulani herdsman invaded Ukpabi Nimbo community in Uzo-Uwani, Enugu State killing more than 100 people with guns, bows, arrows, machetes and swords (Burton, 2017).

According to Ameh (2018), Amnesty International has claimed that clashes between farmers in Adamawa, Benue, Taraba, Ondo, and Kaduna, and the herdsman claimed at least 168 lives in January alone. The attack of Fulani ethnic herdsman has not only been witnessed in

North-Central and South-East alone, farmers in Lagun, Iyana Offa, Offa, Atagba and their surrounding communities in Lagelu Local council Area of Ibadan, Oyo state alleged that a group of Fulani armed men attacked their communities, carted away their valuables (Buzz Nigeria, 2018). Yusuf Turaki alerted that, 'ethnicity' and 'religion' are the two major factors motivating Fulani herdsmen to cause violence in the Middle Belt (Barkindo, 2018).

Factors Responsible for Ethno-Religious Crises

There are some factors that are responsible for ethno-religious conflicts. These include amalgamation, ethnic sentiments, corruption, resource control and religious intolerance.

Amalgamation: The 1914 amalgamation of the Northern and Southern protectorates made up of many ethnic groups with different languages and cultures was the primary cause of ethnic conflicts. Due to multiethnic groups in Nigeria, division has been there along the tribal lines and this incurs hatred, distrust, discrimination, and creates suspicion. The minor ethnic groups are holding grievances against the major ethnic groups because they feel intimidated. Some of the major ethnic groups due to their numerical strength suppress the minor. This tussle deprives the nation of national unity and loyalty.

Ethnic Sentiment: This is ethnic consciousness and loyalty to one's ethnic group. Ethnic loyalty gives rise to ethnic bias and attracts ethnic sentiments. For instance, most government appointments are not done on competence but are done on the basis of tribal sentiments thus encouraging favouritism and preferential treatment. This affects the general unity of the country. This idea of favouritism, for example, the killings by suspected herdsmen in various parts of the country without any decisive government sanction to reprimand them for such act. It is alleged that due to ethnic sentiments on the part of government they were not able to bring them to justice to serve as deterrent to others. Instead the killing of innocent farmers by herdsmen continues.

Corruption: This is a cankerworm eating deep into the fabric of this country. It is the act of dishonest, illegal behaviour, especially from someone in authority with political, religious and economic powers in order to get personal advantage (Gadsby, 1995). Corruption leads to misplacement of the value system, mismanagement of public fund and embezzlement, deflation of the nation's wealth, and affect the sharing of resources. It also lowers respects for the authority. The end result attracts agitation, which can escalate to conflict.

Resource Control: This is a very controversial issue in most countries of the

world because of unfair sharing. This issue of unfair sharing leads to marginalization by those that believe that they are in the corridors of power. For instance, the Niger Delta region are the main oil producing region that generate over 70% of the country's revenue for running the economy of the country. Yet they lack real development in their areas. This attitude of unfair sharing attracts agitation and demands for resource control by ethnic groups that feel oppressed.

Religious Intolerance: Religious fanaticism and bigotry between Christians and Muslims are the major causes of ethno-religious conflicts. Due to differences in religious values and teachings, there is this intolerance existing between Christian and Islamic sects, and this encourages ethnic and religious hostility. The religious differences have been the source of political disagreement at the federal level. More so, before 1999, Nigerian Muslim leaders could not impose Sharia law in their various states. The Constitution of 1999 grants power to Nigeria's States to create a system of appellate court to hear appeals from Sharia trial court. This introduction of Sharia criminal legal system encourages religious intolerance because the views of other religious groups are supposed to be considered before taking such decision. This leads to national controversies and protests, which affect the unity of the country. Again, the idea of writing Arabic language in some of the

denominations of Nigeria's currency is also a kind of religious intolerance. This is because there are other religions existing alongside Islam in Nigeria, therefore their views are to be respected.

Recommendations

A problem detected is already half solved. Disintegration at this point is not helpful. For the promotion and strengthening of national integration, the following recommendations emerged.

Nigeria should rise above the damages caused by colonialism and amalgamation and reverse the structure of the country to benefit every ethnic group and the citizens as well, which includes developing all parts of the country. The leaders should lead by example. This will promote effective transformational leadership. The practice of justice and equity should be encouraged. Employment opportunities should be created to reduce poverty, because poverty promotes desperation. Employment will reduce the vulnerability of the poor to mischief makers. Issues of marginalization and resource control should not be neglected. It is important to create sense of balance and share the country's resources fairly and avoid marginalization of any ethnic group.

Citizens should remember that Nigeria is one nation, and should bear in mind that the National Flag, National Anthem and National

Pledge remind Nigerians that we have same identity; therefore, the spirit of oneness, common code of behaviour, socio-cultural unity, and common ideas of life should be encouraged. Citizens should observe the fundamental human rights, which state that each person is equal in every way. People should not be discriminated against on the basis of differences in ethnicity, religion language and culture.

Government should not have preference to one religion at the detriment or expense of another, since Nigeria is a secular state. Each citizen should be allowed to exercise his or her right to practice his or her religion. Government should device a way to deal thoroughly with religious extremists, since their activities affect the spirit of national unity and integration.

There is this need to include multiethnic education in education curriculum to sensitize the students on the existing cultural backgrounds and the need to respect their existence. This will help to reduce prejudices among the citizens. It will also help them to appreciate diverse members of Nigerian nation. Leaders of various religious sects should constantly remind their members to uphold positive religious values like love, forgiveness, tolerance, peace and unity to promote national integration, unity and progress. The communication system and mass media should help to publicize to all, the culture of different regions of Nigeria through their programmes

and publications, on a common code of behaviour and ideas of life. This will also help to harness the country's peace, unity and integrity.

Conclusion

Conflict is a very old phenomenon, which is a recurring decimal in human existence. It features in most areas of human endeavour, if not all. There are levels of conflicts, which range from personal, societal, economic, ethnic and religious conflicts, among others. From this paper it has been revealed that ethnicity and religion are the major causes of conflicts in Nigerian contemporary society. These have posed problems and it is a big challenge to the socio-political and economic lives of the citizens. This adversely threatens the unity, stability, integration and peaceful co-existence in the country.

In this paper, an effort is made to examine the problems of ethno-religious crises in heterogeneous and pluralistic society like Nigeria, the factors that are responsible for this problem emerged, which include: 1914 amalgamation, ethnic sentiment, corruption, resource control mismanagement and religious intolerance. This paper made some recommendations for meaningful co-existence and integration in multiethnic Nigerian society.

This paper argues that the full acceptance and implementations of the suggested recommendations will help Nigerian

multiethnic society to be free from conflicts and enjoy a democratic society, respect for human life and human dignity irrespective of cultural, ethnic and religious background and differences. Therefore, Nigeria is supposed to harness the diversities of culture and ethnic groups towards national development since it creates avenues for healthy competition in economic development. With these, Nigeria will evolve from the society of ethno-religious conflicts to enjoy peace, justice, equity and fairness, and build a strong and united nation.

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